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Abstract

This report presents the SCOPE+i Framework, a tailored infrastructure developed within the GraspOS project to support the implementation of Responsible Research Assessment (RRA). Building on the SCOPE Framework created by the INORMS Research Evaluation Group, SCOPE+i extends it with assessment process resources and assessment services that facilitate collaborative planning, documentation, and registration of assessment activities. The framework includes seventeen process resources – templates, guides, and checklists – that support all stages of the SCOPE process, from initial planning to evaluation. Two assessment services, the Openness Profile and the Assessment Protocol Portfolio (APP), are integrated within the GraspOS Open Infrastructure and underpinned by Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) to ensure interoperability. Together, they enable transparent, context-sensitive, and evidence-based approaches to research assessment across diverse institutional and disciplinary settings.

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Abbreviation List

API - Application Programming Interface
APP - Assessment Protocol Portfolio
ARRA - Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment
CoARA - Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CRedit - Contributor Role Taxonomy
CRIS - Current Research Information System
DOI - Digital Object Identifier
DORA - Declaration on Research Assessment
EDI - Equity, Diversity, Inclusion
EOSC - European Open Science Cloud
FAIR - Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
GraspOS - Next Generation Research Assessment to Promote Open Science
INORMS - International Network of Research Management Societies
JIF - Journal Impact Factor
ORCID - Open Researcher and Contributor ID
OS - Open Science
OSAF - Open Science Assessment Framework
PID - Persistent Identifier
RA - Research Assessment
RAiD - Research Activity Identifier
RDA - Resource Description and Access
RFO - Research Funding Organisation
ROR - Research Organization Registry
RPO - Research Performing Organisation

RRA - Responsible Research Assessment
RSE - Research Software Engineer
SCOPE - Start with what you value, Context considerations, Options for Evaluating, Probe Deeply, Evaluate your Evaluation
SCOPE+i - SCOPE plus infrastructure
SEP - Strategy Evaluation Protocol
SKG - Scientific Knowledge Graph
UI - User Interface
WP - Work Package

1. Executive summary

This report introduces the SCOPE+i Framework, a tailored infrastructure developed to support the implementation and opening of Responsible Research Assessment (RRA). The framework builds on, and takes its name from, the SCOPE Framework for Research Evaluation developed by the INORMS Research Evaluation Group (INORMS REG), augmenting it with supporting infrastructure (+i) designed to make research assessment processes more transparent, collaborative, and inclusive.

Co-developed with the GraspOS pilots, the SCOPE+i Framework consists of two main components: assessment process resources and assessment services. The process resources provide structured guidance for operationalising the transition to RRA, while the assessment services enable the collaborative collection, sharing, and registration of assessment plans and designs—key steps in opening research assessment.

The process resources are available in three formats—templates, guides, and checklists—and together they support all stages of the SCOPE process, from initial planning through to evaluating the evaluation itself. Seventeen resources are currently available, offering practical support for defining values, documenting context, and publishing assessment protocols. These resources can be used for assessments of individual researchers as well as groups or organisations.

The two assessment services developed within the SCOPE+i Framework are the Openness Profile and the Assessment Protocol Portfolio (APP). Both are part of the GraspOS Open Infrastructure and are technically underpinned by the Research Activity Identifier (RAiD), which ensures persistent identification and interoperability.

The Openness Profile makes visible the diversity of Open Science (OS) contributions by allowing flexible input of various types of evidence, including narratives that help

contextualise individual contributions. The Assessment Protocol Portfolio (APP) supports the planning and documentation of research assessment by performing two key functions: recording the agreed approach for a specific assessment event and registering the assessment protocol once the event concludes. Together, they act as shared resources for conducting, recording, and opening research assessment.

2. Introduction and background

The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) challenges us to develop more meaningful and equitable ways of evaluating research and researchers. This shift requires moving away from an overreliance on quantitative indicators—such as citation counts and journal impact factors—toward a broader, more holistic view that values diverse research practices and contributions.

CoARA's **Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment¹ (ARRA)** sets out a forward-looking framework built around four main commitments. First, it calls for recognizing the varied ways researchers contribute to their fields and the unique career paths they may follow, ensuring that assessment practices are tailored to the needs of each research area. Second, it promotes **qualitative evaluation** as the primary basis for assessment, with peer review at the core, while supporting the responsible use of quantitative indicators as complementary evidence. Third, ARRA urges the abandonment of inappropriate use of metrics such as the Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and the h-index, as they risk narrowing the scope of what is considered valuable. Finally, it discourages reliance on rankings in assessment, as they often oversimplify and misrepresent the complexity of research quality and impact. Together, these commitments aim to establish more meaningful and inclusive approaches to research assessment.

Implementing such practices requires **institutional transformation**—shifting from metrics-based evaluations to more nuanced, qualitative approaches that consider factors such as Open Science (OS), societal impact, and interdisciplinary work. This transformation also relies on the active engagement of stakeholders—including researchers, institutional leaders, and evaluators—to co-define criteria and ensure transparency. By adopting a collaborative and inclusive approach to **opening research assessment**, institutions can build support for reform, align with evolving research

¹ Arentoft, M., Berghmans, S., Borrell-Damian, L., Bottaro, S., Faure, J.-E., Gaillard, V., Glinos, K., Albacete, J. L., Morais, R., Morris, J., Schiltz, M., & Stroobants, K. (2022). Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13480728>

priorities, and embed a culture of fair, transparent, and impactful evaluation within their core processes.

3. Methodology

Building on the principle of adopting a collaborative and inclusive approach to opening research assessment, this report introduces the **SCOPE+i Framework**—a tailored infrastructure designed to support the implementation of Responsible Research Assessment (RRA). The framework builds on, and takes its name from, the SCOPE Framework for Research Evaluation (Figure 1) developed by the INORMS Research Evaluation Group (INORMS REG)², extending it with supporting infrastructure that enables shared planning, documentation, and reflection across the assessment process.

Figure 1 Five stages of the SCOPE Framework

² SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

The SCOPE Framework complements the principles of the ARRA and has already proven valuable in advancing RRA. It rests on three core principles:

1. **Evaluate only where necessary**—recognizing that sometimes it is more effective to incentivize desired behaviors than to assess them.
2. **Evaluate with the evaluated**—ensuring that evaluations are co-designed and interpreted with input from the communities being assessed, making them more relevant and inclusive.
3. **Draw on evaluation expertise**—applying the same rigor to evaluation processes as is expected in academic research itself.

Through these principles, the SCOPE Framework fosters a thoughtful, collaborative, and expertise-driven approach to assessment, closely aligned with ARRA's goals.

The SCOPE+i Framework adapts this approach for the ambitions of GraspOS. It was specifically co-designed as a companion to the SCOPE process, developed in close collaboration with the nine GraspOS pilots that used SCOPE in their activities.

Put simply: SCOPE + infrastructure = SCOPE+i.

This infrastructure consists of two main components:

- **Assessment process resources (SCOPE+i Resources)**, which provide guidance for implementing key elements of RRA, and
- **Digital services (SCOPE+i Services)**, which enable collaborative collection and sharing of assessment plans and documentation throughout the assessment process.

Development and refinement of the SCOPE+i Framework were strongly shaped by the **GraspOS piloting process**, carried out in collaboration with WP5 Pilots, WP3 Services, and WP4 Federated Open Infrastructure. This co-development approach included regular alignment meetings and a series of online and in-person workshops focused on specific SCOPE+i topics.

In the early stages of pilot assessment projects, workshops explored initial SCOPE+i Resources such as stakeholder mapping template, value statement template, and purpose statement template. In later stages, pilots focused on SCOPE+i Services, such as the **Openness Profile**—with some developing demos or mock-ups to test profile features. In the final stage, pilot representatives provided direct feedback on the full

suite of SCOPE+i Resources, helping to refine the framework and ensure its usability in diverse research settings.

3.1 Context Shaping Assessment Design

The GraspOS pilots highlighted that each evaluation setting is highly context-specific, showing that there can be no “one-size-fits-all” approach to assessment. Pilots differed in their levels, purpose, priorities, and stakeholder mix. Early efforts to align them revealed that too much standardisation risks overlooking these important differences. This became a valuable learning point: context should be treated as central to how assessments are designed and carried out³.

This recognition extends to Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) more generally. RRA is still an evolving initiative, and its implementation benefits from acknowledging that different institutions, disciplines, and national systems bring their own conditions and priorities. Expecting uniform solutions at this stage may narrow possibilities rather than support progress. Learning from GraspOS pilots emphasises the need to treat contextual variation as an asset rather than a problem.

Context shapes assessment design through the values, purposes, and conditions that determine what is considered important in a given setting. These may include disciplinary norms, institutional constraints, the maturity of infrastructure, stakeholder involvement, and the capacity for systemic change. Such factors form the foundation of an assessment, giving it meaning by clarifying what is being evaluated and why.

This perspective aligns with the SCOPE Framework, which stresses the primacy of values and context in assessment reform. Both SCOPE and the CoARA commitments place qualitative considerations at the center, supporting peer review to operate within assessment designs that are inclusive and relevant. Narrative CVs illustrate this principle: they provide value when used to frame how contributions are understood and assessed within a particular community.

These insights reinforce the importance of **flexibility** in the SCOPE+i Framework. Its process resources and digital services are intended to facilitate assessment design without constraining it, supporting institutions in adapting assessment practices to their own contexts. In this way, SCOPE+i aims to provide structured guidance while leaving

³ Himanen, L. (2025). Deliverable 5.3: Pilot findings and progress report (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17035609>

space for diversity—helping to advance more responsible, transparent, and **context-sensitive approaches** to research assessment.

4. SCOPE+i Framework

As noted above, the GraspOS project has developed tailored infrastructure, called the **SCOPE+i Framework**, which builds on the existing SCOPE Framework. This assessment infrastructure consists of two main components: assessment process resources and digital services. The assessment process resources offer guidance for implementing key elements of Responsible Research Assessment (RRA), while the digital services enable collaborative collection and sharing of assessment plans and documentation throughout the entire assessment process.

The SCOPE+i Framework is designed to support the RRA transition, with a particular emphasis on contributions to Open Science (OS). By integrating process resources and digital services into the SCOPE process, the SCOPE+i Framework combines the flexibility required to plan and conduct RRA in diverse assessment contexts with practical tools for managing the complexities of research assessment reform.

In this framework, *assessment processes* refer to the activities involved in planning and carrying out research assessments. The process resources are focused on operationalizing the transition to RRA. This set of resources is provided in three formats; templates, guides, and checklists. *Digital services* refer to assessment-specific services aligned with contemporary interoperability standards for research information systems. The two services are an **Openness Profile** – a portfolio for making visible contributions to OS – and an **Assessment Protocol Portfolio** for use during the full assessment event.

4.1 SCOPE+i Resources

The process resources are focused on operationalizing the transition to RRA. This set of resources is provided in three formats: templates, guides, and checklists. Where possible existing resources are adapted, like for example the Royal Society Résumé for Researchers to develop guidance on employing an OS Narrative CV template. In most cases, the process resources are intended to facilitate SCOPE activities, such as providing a values statement template. The SCOPE+i Resources draw on insights from

the GraspOS landscape analysis⁴ for OS aware RRA, together with observations from the GraspOS pilots throughout the project. The aim of the full set of process resources is to support the planning, design, and documentation of responsible research assessment events, while respecting the flexibility needed to implement them in local contexts.

These resources can be used independently or together with the assessment services to address:

1. different assessment phases: assessment readiness, assessment protocol, assessment execution, and assessment evaluation & dissemination
2. the five SCOPE stages: Start with what you value, Context considerations, Options for evaluation, Probe deeply and Evaluate your evaluation

Assessment process resources (Figure 2) have been created for each assessment phase. In total seventeen resources – checklists, guides and templates - support the SCOPE process, which addresses initial planning through to the evaluation of the evaluation. The resources also support publication of assessment protocols. Resources can be used to support the assessment of researchers as well as other types and sizes of research entities like research groups or organizations. All 17 practical resources are openly published in Zenodo, in the [GraspOS Templates & Guidelines community](#).

⁴ Anna-Kaisa Hyrkkänen, Dragan Ivanović, Janne Pölonen, Marita Kari, & Elina Pylvänäinen. (2023). GraspOS Deliverable D2.1 "OS-aware RRA approaches landscape report". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11098095>

SCOPE+i RESOURCES		SCOPE				
		S	C	O	P	E
Guide for assembling an assessment team G		●	●			
Value statement template T		●				
Purpose and context statement template T			●			
Guide on choosing an assessment method G				●	●	
Stakeholder mapping template T		●	●			
Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators G				●	●	
Indicators guide 2: Frameworks and toolboxes for open research G		●	●	●	●	●
Open Science assessment guide G		●	●			
Guide on the diversity of OS contributions, roles and activities G				●	●	
Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV G				●	●	
Guide on equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) in research assessment G		●	●			
Checklist for responsible research assessment C		●	●	●	●	●
Guide for evaluating the assessment process G						●
Guide on principles for responsible research assessment for evaluators and evaluands G				●	●	
Assessment readiness template T		●	●			
Guide for overcoming common obstacles in implementing RRA G				●	●	
Institutional assessment process checklist C				●	●	

G = GUIDE **T** = TEMPLATE **C** = CHECKLIST

Figure 2 illustration of the checklists, guides, and templates in relation to the SCOPE stages

Next are the texts of the actionable versions of the seventeen resources. Actionable versions are two-pages summaries based on full (long) resources of the SCOPE+i Resources which are published in Zenodo along with the actionable versions.

4.1.1 Guide for Assembling an Assessment Team

Definition

An assessment team is a group of people with complementary expertise who design, manage, and implement research assessment (RA) processes. Teams can include professionals from research services, HR, library, IT, or external stakeholders.

This guide helps identify the types of expertise, roles and tasks required within a research assessment team. It is particularly useful for individuals responsible for designing, managing, or overseeing the assessment process.

Relevant SCOPE Stages

This guide is relevant in the early stages of the SCOPE Framework:

- Start with what you value: Identify values that should guide the composition of the team (e.g., diversity, fairness, openness).
- Context considerations: Ensure team expertise, roles, and composition fit the assessment's goals, scope, and institutional context.

When and How to Use

- Planning assessments: When preparing a new research assessment process or reviewing existing processes.
- Recruitment and promotions: Assemble teams that combine disciplinary expertise with knowledge of open science and EDI principles.
- Strategic evaluations: Ensure inclusion of cross-disciplinary and stakeholder perspectives (e.g., industry, societal actors).
- Ongoing RRA reforms: Use diverse, rotating teams to bring in new perspectives and share lessons learned across the institution.

Guidance

Clarify roles and responsibilities

- Distinguish between planning, facilitation, and implementation roles.
- Clearly define leadership, coordination, and reporting responsibilities.

Ensure breadth of expertise

- Cover disciplinary knowledge, open science, EDI, ethical and cultural awareness, qualitative and quantitative methods, impact assessment, and data management.
- Balance permanent institutional staff with rotating experts.

Apply RRA principles

- Follow guidance from e.g. DORA, CoARA, and Leiden Manifesto.
- Use chosen methods responsibly.
- Be mindful of unintended consequences, workload, and fairness.

Promote diversity and inclusion

- Ensure representation across career stages, genders, disciplines, and cultural backgrounds in the team.

Strengthen communication and efficiency

- Foster transparent dialogue among stakeholders.
- Share lessons learned across teams and institutions.
- Consider the cost-benefit balance of time-intensive evaluations.

Table 1 *Examples of roles and tasks*

Roles / Expertise	Typical Tasks
Coordinator / Project Manager	Overall planning, coordination, reporting, communication
Disciplinary Expert	Provide field-specific knowledge
EDI Specialist	Ensure equity, diversity, and inclusion considerations
Open Science Expert	Promote open science practices
Data Analyst	Conduct quantitative analysis, data quality checks, visualization
Evaluator (peer review)	Qualitative assessment, impact evaluation, fairness checks

Further Reading

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resources

- Stakeholder Mapping Template: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525686>
- Guide on principles for responsible research assessment for evaluators and evaluands: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526025>

- Checklist for Responsible Research Assessment:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524455>
- Guide on Equity, Diversity and Inclusion in Research Assessment:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526122>
- Institutional assessment process checklist:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526008>

Other

- Recommendations on research assessment processes (Science Europe, 2020).
Position Statement
<https://www.scienceeurope.org/media/3twjxim0/se-position-statement-research-assessment-processes.pdf>
- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

4.1.2 Value Statement Template

Definition

The Value Statement Template helps organisations identify and articulate the values that underpin their research assessment (RA) criteria. Values define the target of evaluation and guide in the choice of methods, materials and data used, and indicators. A clearly defined value statement is a starting point of a research assessment process.

This template provides a structured way to specify:

- Super-values (broad guiding principles, e.g., openness, diversity).
- Values (how super-values are expressed, e.g., diversity of careers).
- Sub-values (practical indicators, e.g., assessing performance relative to opportunities, like working as a reviewer).

Relevant SCOPE stages

This resource is most relevant in SCOPE stage:

- Start with what you value: Defining and prioritising values is the foundation of responsible evaluation.

It also informs later stages: choosing options (O), probing deeply (P), and evaluating (E), since values guide decisions throughout the RA process.

When and how to use

Use this template when:

- Starting any research assessment process (e.g., recruitment, promotion, funding allocation).

How to use:

- Engage stakeholders (HR, researchers, leadership) to agree on shared values.
- List super-values (e.g., openness, inclusivity, quality).
- Translate super-values into values (e.g., inclusivity → diversity of careers and disciplines).
- Define sub-values with concrete examples (e.g., inclusivity → recognition of career breaks, multilingual publishing, mentoring)
- Document value statements in the provided template and use them as the basis for defining assessment criteria, metrics, and processes.
- Review and update periodically to reflect evolving priorities and practices.

Guidance

- Be explicit: Make values transparent and shared across the organisation.
- Balance breadth and detail: Use super-values for direction, values for clarity, and sub-values for practical implementation.
- Link indicators to values
- Support cultural change: Values-based assessment helps move away from narrow metrics (e.g., journal impact factor) toward holistic evaluation.
- Engage collaboratively: Involve staff at all levels to ensure legitimacy and buy-in.

Further reading

SCOPE+i Resources

- Guide on choosing an assessment method: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525721>
- Guide on equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) in research assessment: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526122>

Other

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- Science Europe (2023): Recognising What We Value: recommendation on Recognition Systems <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7858100>

4.1.3 Purpose and Context Statement Template

Definition

The Purpose and Context Statement Template helps organisations define and document the purpose and setting of research assessment (RA). It ensures that evaluation activities are tailored to their intended goals and contexts. By clarifying why assessment is being done, who or what is being assessed, and under which disciplinary, institutional, and cultural conditions, the template supports responsible, transparent, and fit-for-purpose research assessment.

Relevant SCOPE stages

This resource is most relevant to:

- Context considerations: Understanding the environment, purpose, and level of the assessment before choosing methods.

It also informs S (Start with what you value) and O (Options for evaluating), since values and context together guide what indicators and approaches are most appropriate.

When and how to use

Use this template when:

- Planning any new RA process (e.g., recruitment, promotion, funding allocation, evaluation of departments or institutions).
- Revising existing RA practices to ensure they are aligned with organisational values, disciplinary norms, and international frameworks.
- Contextualising evaluations in multi-disciplinary, national, or global settings.

How to use:

- Define the purpose → Is the assessment for monitoring, learning, improvement, or resource allocation?
- Identify the level of evaluation → Individual researcher, group, department, institution? Consider the size and type of organisation.
- Analyse disciplinary context → Map typical outputs, activities, and norms in the field. Consider data coverage, balance between basic and applied research, and inter-sectoral orientation.

- Consider other contextual factors → National and cultural conditions, funding systems, language practices, geopolitical or societal challenges.
- Document clearly → Use the template to record all of the above and ensure transparency in RA protocols.

Guidance

- Avoid one-size-fits-all approaches: Different contexts require tailored criteria.
- Recognise disciplinary diversity: Outputs vary (e.g., datasets, policy briefs, monographs, exhibitions, software). Adjust assessments accordingly.
- Consider inclusivity and equity: Reflect on equity, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) when evaluating individuals or groups.
- Integrate with values: Use in combination with the Value Statement Template to align purpose/context with what the organisation values.
- Ensure transparency: Make purpose and contextual considerations explicit in protocols so evaluators and evaluands understand the framework.
- Review regularly: Update the template to reflect changes in national research systems, institutional priorities, or disciplinary practices.

Further reading

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resources

- Guide on choosing an assessment method:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525721>
- Guide on equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) in research assessment:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526122>

Other

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- European Commission (2019), Indicator frameworks for fostering open knowledge practices in science and scholarship
<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/445286>

4.1.4 Guide on Choosing an Assessment Method

Definition

Guide on choosing an assessment method supports selecting tools, approaches, and infrastructures to evaluate research and researchers in a way that aligns with institutional values and goals.

Relevant SCOPE Stages

This guide is most relevant for the SCOPE stages:

- Option for evaluating: Identifying different methods (qualitative, quantitative, narrative, self-assessment, surveys) and data sources.
- Probe deeply: Weighing advantages, limitations, impacts, and unintended consequences of methods before applying them.

When and How to Use

- Recruitment & promotion & career assessment: Ensure methods are consistent with institutional values and avoid reliance on journal-based metrics. Base assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation, supported by responsible use of indicators.
- Strategic planning: Use large-scale metrics responsibly for benchmarking and resource allocation at organisational or national level.
- Rewarding & recognition: Consider open science practices, teaching, leadership, societal engagement, and collaboration, not just publications.

Guidance

Start with value

- Define what your organisation values (e.g., openness, interdisciplinarity, quality, societal impact).
- Document values using a Value Statement Template.

Match method to purpose and level of evaluation

- Individuals: Use qualitative methods (peer review, narrative CV, impact stories). Quantitative indicators should only support expert judgment.
- Groups/organisations: Combine self-assessment, surveys, and carefully chosen metrics

- Large entities (national/disciplinary): Metrics and benchmarking are useful but should always be contextualised.

Combine methods for balance

- Use more than one method to capture diversity and avoid bias.
- Involve the assessed community in interpreting results.

Use metrics responsibly

- Follow DORA, Leiden Manifesto, Metric Tide and CoARA principles: be clear, transparent, contextual, specific, and fair.
- Avoid journal-based metrics for individual evaluation.
- Always align indicators with assessment objectives.

Choose data infrastructures carefully

- Prefer open, transparent, and interoperable systems (e.g., OpenAIRE, OpenAlex, ORCID).
- Avoid relying only on traditional or commercial databases that limit coverage or reinforce biases.

Further Reading

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resources

- Indicators guide1: Responsible use of indicators.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>
- Indicators guide 2: Indicators Guide 2: Frameworks and toolboxes for open research <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17181862>
- Open Science Assessment Guide: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525630>
- Assessment Readiness Template: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525577>
- Guide for assembling an assessment team:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525548>
- Value statement template: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524532>
- Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525987>
- Guide on principles for responsible research assessment for evaluators and evaluands: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526025>

Other

- European Commission (2019), Indicator frameworks for fostering open knowledge practices in science and scholarship
<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/445286>
- Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information (2024):
<https://barcelona-declaration.org/>
- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

4.1.5 Stakeholder Mapping Template

Definition

This template supports the identification and documentation of stakeholders in research assessment (RA) processes. Stakeholder mapping is critical because effective RA requires a diversity of perspectives, expertise, and experiences. The template prompts you to list stakeholders by category (e.g., researchers, HR, administration, funders, national bodies) and to record their roles and contributions to the process.

Relevant SCOPE Stages

The template is particularly useful in the following SCOPE stages:

- Start with what you value: clarify institutional values and priorities by identifying who defines them.
- Context considerations: map the environment, actors, and power dynamics that shape the RA process.

When and How to Use

When:

- At the start of a research assessment process.
- When reviewing or designing assessment protocols or career development frameworks.
- During preparation of self-evaluations or strategic planning of e.g. institutions to ensure inclusivity.

How:

- Map all relevant stakeholders, grouping them into categories (e.g., researchers, management, HR, funders, bibliometricians, national stakeholders).
- Specify their roles and activities (e.g., evaluator, coordinator, data provider, reporting, decision-making).
- Use the map to check diversity of representation, avoid blind spots, and ensure all critical perspectives are included.

Guidance

- For HR and administration: ensure staff policies, recruitment, and career development stakeholders are represented.
- For researchers and managers: balance voices across disciplines, seniority levels, and demographic diversity.
- For executive leadership: recognise the influence of external stakeholders (e.g., ministries, funders, indexing services).
- For assessment coordinators: use the mapping to plan communication, define responsibilities, and distribute tasks.

Tips for effective use:

- Begin broad, then refine - missing stakeholders can undermine fairness and credibility.
- Document both formal roles (decision-making, evaluation) and informal contributions (advice, advocacy).
- Revisit and update the map throughout the RA process.

Further Reading

GraspOS SCOPE+I Resources

- Guide for assembling an assessment team.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525548>

Other

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

4.1.6 Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators

Definition

This guide supports responsible research assessment (RRA) with a special focus on open science (OS) contributions. It provides guidance on how to select, interpret, and apply indicators and metrics in a way that balances quantitative measures with qualitative judgment. Its main purpose is to help institutions use indicators transparently, responsibly, and in alignment with their values.

Relevant SCOPE stages

- Options for evaluating: Choosing appropriate indicators and metrics.
- Probe deeply: Interpreting data critically and acknowledging limitations.

When and how to use

Use the guide when:

- Designing or revising research assessment processes (e.g., for hiring, promotion, funding).
- Developing balanced evaluation frameworks that combine quantitative metrics with qualitative expert assessment.
- Benchmarking at institutional, national, or disciplinary levels.
- Introducing or strengthening recognition of open science practices in career assessment.

How to use:

- Define purpose and values → What do you want to measure, and why?
- Select indicators responsibly → Use multiple indicators instead of relying on a single metric.
- Balance methods → Combine metrics (e.g., citations, downloads, collaboration data) with qualitative evaluation (peer review, narrative CVs).
- Ensure transparency → Clearly state which indicators are used, their data sources, and limitations.
- Revisit regularly → Assess whether chosen indicators remain fit for purpose.

Guidance

- Avoid misuse of metrics: Journal Impact Factor and H-index should not be applied in evaluating individual researchers.
- Context matters: Citation and publication practices differ across disciplines. Always interpret metrics relative to the field, (evaluation's?)purpose and values.
- Prioritise openness: Use open infrastructures (e.g. OpenAlex, OpenAIRE, BIPIServices, OpenCitations) in line with the Barcelona Declaration.
- Highlight OS practices: Consider indicators for open access, FAIR data, open peer review, collaboration, and societal impact.
- Remember limitations: Indicators often reflect past activity and miss broader contributions such as open teaching material or mentoring.
- Interpret cautiously, especially for individuals.

Further reading

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resources

- Indicators Guide 2: Frameworks and toolboxes for open research <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17181862>
- Open Science assessment guide <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525630>
- Guide on choosing an assessment method <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525721>

Other

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- Leiden Manifesto: <https://www.leidenmanifesto.org/>
- DORA Declaration & Guidance: <https://sfedora.org/read/>

4.1.7 Indicators Guide 2: Frameworks and Toolboxes for Open Research

Definition

This resource outlines a process for choosing indicators aimed at assessing Open Research. The process relies on two concepts: an **indicator framework** and an **indicator toolbox**⁵. The indicator framework is context-specific decision lens that sets out why, for whom, and under what conditions indicators will be used. Whereas, the indicator toolbox is the curated collection of potential indicators, qualitative and quantitative, organized and documented with the rationale for each selected indicator. The framework and toolbox work together. The indicator framework provides the strategy for selecting and using indicators, while the toolbox supplies and documents the chosen indicators and their application. This guide draws on the European Commission report: *Indicator frameworks for fostering open knowledge practices in science and scholarship* (2019).

Relevant SCOPE stages

(S) Start with what you value, (C) Context Considerations, (O) Options for Evaluation, (P) Probe Deeply, and (E) Evaluate your Evaluation)

When and How to use

Developing an indicator framework for research evaluation requires careful consideration of multiple analytical dimensions related to the purpose and context of use. Engaging stakeholders in a reflective process to determine which indicators are most appropriate enhances the relevance, credibility, and utility of the evaluation. This guide offers a high-level overview of the considerations in preparing an indicator framework and indicator toolbox, with the recommendation that the process engages relevant stakeholders and practitioners such as: researchers, evaluators, data and metrics specialists, and policy or funding representatives.

Guidance

The following six steps guide the design of an indicator framework and the development of an indicator toolbox for an assessment in a specific context. Select the steps that fit the assessment. Each chosen step contributes to an overall strategy for indicator selection (the indicator framework). After the framework is finalized, indicators

⁵ Indicator frameworks for fostering open knowledge practices in science and scholarship (2019).

are collaboratively chosen and documented to create an indicator toolbox tailored to the assessment.

1. Clarify Goal of Assessment

Ask: Why is an indicator needed?

Monitoring → system-level trends using aggregate measures.

Learning → context-rich, qualitative or mixed evidence.

Resource allocation / career assessment → balance comparability with accuracy.

Action: Define the main purpose to guide later indicator choices.

2. Identify Values (from the SCOPE process)

Ask: Which SCOPE-derived values (e.g., equity, transparency) will anchor the assessment?

Action: Revisit the SCOPE discussions with stakeholders that lead to values. Articulate how each chosen value should shape research practices and evaluation goals. Map the identified sub-values to desired research practices (e.g., equity → global access and capacity building; transparency → reproducible workflows). Record the kinds of evidence that will later demonstrate these practices, without yet selecting specific indicators.

3. Specify Level of Assessment

Ask: At what level will indicators operate—system, organizational, or individual/group?

Action: Match indicator types to the chosen level and guard against misusing system-level metrics for individual evaluation.

4. Examine Disciplinary and Research Approaches

Ask: How do methods and knowledge producing cultures shape openness?

Action: Capture relevant knowledge-creation and sharing modes; plan for co-design with the research community.

5. Map Stakeholders, Audiences, and Beneficiaries

Ask: Whose engagement and benefit matter most (e.g., researchers, funders, citizens)?

Action: Plan indicators that can later show meaningful interactions and check for inclusiveness and potential bias.

6. Assess the Research Environment

Ask: Which enabling or constraining conditions apply (e.g., policies, infrastructure, funding)?

Action: Anticipate indicators that reflect environmental readiness or constraints and adjust expectations accordingly.

Further reading

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resources

- Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>
- European Commission (2019): Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Schomberg, R., Britt Holbrook, J., Oancea, A., Kamerlin, S. et al., Indicator frameworks for fostering open knowledge practices in science and scholarship, Publications Office, 2019, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/44528>
- Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Guide on choosing an assessment method. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525721>
- Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Purpose and context statement template. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525469>

Other

- European Commission (2019): Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Schomberg, R., Britt Holbrook, J., Oancea, A., Kamerlin, S. et al., Indicator frameworks for fostering open knowledge practices in science and scholarship, Publications Office, 2019, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/44528>
- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023), <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

4.1.8 Open Science Assessment Guide

Definition

This guide highlights Open Science (OS) outputs, activities and contributions that are relevant to consider in all types of OS aware research assessment (RA) processes.

Open Science (OS) refers to research practices that make scientific knowledge accessible, transparent, reusable, and inclusive. It covers open access to publications, open and FAIR data, open methodologies and software, open peer review, citizen science, and broader engagement with society. In the context of research assessment, OS-aware research assessment means valuing contributions beyond traditional journal articles, recognising data sharing, collaborative practices, teaching, mentoring, leadership, and other activities that support transparent and inclusive research.

Relevant SCOPE Stages

This resource aligns most strongly with the early stages of the SCOPE Framework:

- Start with what you value.
- Context considerations: Adapt OS assessment practices to disciplinary norms, national policies, and institutional missions.

Later stages (Options, Probe, Evaluate) remain important for piloting and refining implementation.

When and How to Use

Use this guide when e.g.:

- Designing or updating recruitment, promotion, or tenure criteria.
- Reviewing grant, fellowship, or award applications.
- Developing institutional assessment policies aligned with e.g. ARRA or UNESCO recommendations.

Guidance

- Integrate monitoring: Shift from output-only tracking to assessing processes, outcomes, and long-term impacts.
- Update HR and assessment forms to allow for OS contributions such as datasets, software, protocols, mentoring.
- Pilot new assessment approaches e.g. narrative CV, openness profile with evaluators and researchers.
- Identify relevant outputs and activities using open databases e.g. OpenAIRE, OpenAlex, BIP!Services.
- Broaden recognition: Value diverse outputs (datasets, software, preprints, protocols, non-English outputs).
- Recognise roles and activities: Teaching, mentoring, leadership, citizen science, outreach, and engagement.
- Adopt FAIR and PIDs: Encourage use of ORCID, DOIs, and open licensing for findability and reusability.
- Acknowledge practices: Reward openness, reproducibility, inclusivity, collaboration, and peer review.
- Ensure equity: Consider structural constraints e.g. costs of OA, disciplinary differences.
- Train assessors and researchers: Provide guidance on narrative CVs, responsible metrics, and OS tools.

- Use incentives: Offer recognition in promotion, salary bonuses, awards, or badges for OS practices.

Further Reading

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resources

- Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525987>
- Guide on the diversity of OS contributions, roles and activities
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526089>

Other

- European Commission (2019): Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Schomberg, R., Britt Holbrook, J., Oancea, A., Kamerlin, S. et al., Indicator frameworks for fostering open knowledge practices in science and scholarship, Publications Office, 2019, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/44528>
- Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA, 2022), CoARA, [The Agreement - CoARA](#)
- UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021), [Draft Recommendation on Open Educational Resources - UNESCO Digital Library](#)
- Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information (2024), <https://barcelona-declaration.org/>
- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

4.1.9 Guide on Diversity of Open Science Contributions, Roles and Activities

Definition

This guide highlights the diversity of open science (OS) contributions, roles, and activities that should be recognised in research assessment and career evaluation. It emphasises that scholarly contributions extend beyond publications and citations, encompassing data sharing, software, citizen science, mentoring, infrastructure support, and stakeholder engagement. The goal is to support responsible research assessment (RRA) by valuing contributions that make research more transparent, inclusive, equitable, and societally relevant.

Relevant SCOPE stages

This guide is most relevant in SCOPE stages:

- Options for evaluating: Identifying diverse OS contributions and roles to include in assessment.
- Probe deeply: Critically reviewing how these contributions are acknowledged and ensuring fairness across disciplines and roles.

When and how to use

Use this guide when:

- Designing assessment protocols for recruitment, promotion, or funding that go beyond publications.
- Implementing narrative CVs that allow researchers to showcase OS practices.
- Recognising team science and collaboration, where not all contributions are reflected in authorship.
- Engaging stakeholders (policy-makers, practitioners, citizen scientists) in assessment frameworks.

How to use:

- Map contributions broadly → Include activities such as data curation, software development, mentoring, open peer review, and citizen science.
- Consider multiple stakeholders → Acknowledge contributions from librarians, data stewards, infrastructure staff, and other enablers of OS.
- Integrate OS into skills frameworks → Ensure assessments value skills in data management, openness, collaboration, and public engagement.
- Adapt to context → Weight contributions differently depending on discipline, career stage, and role.

Guidance

- Shift from narrow metrics: Avoid evaluating researchers only through publications and citations; include diverse OS outputs and activities.
- Recognise invisible contributions: Value contributions that enable OS also from non-academic staff.
- Apply CRediT taxonomy → Use the Contributor Role Taxonomy (14 roles, e.g. conceptualization, data curation, software, supervision) to capture diverse contributions

- Encourage inclusivity and equity: consider contributions to citizen science, public engagement, and collaboration with underrepresented communities.
- Support systemic change: Align assessment systems with UNESCO OS principles transparency, inclusiveness, equity, sustainability.
- Use open infrastructures and tools: Examples include EOSC (European Open Science Cloud), OpenEdition, HAL, Episciences, Jisc Open Policy Finder.
- Value OS skills: Ensure training, recognition, and reward systems encourage data sharing, collaboration, and engagement.
- Foster cultural change: Organisations that have signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) should integrate OS contributions explicitly into their assessment practices.

Further reading

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resources

- Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525987>

Other

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- CRediT Contributor Role Taxonomy (ANSI/NISO, 2022): <https://credit.niso.org/>
- Open Science Skills Visualisation (McCaffrey et al., 2020):
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4727592>

4.1.10 Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV

Definitions

This two-page summary provides **actionable direction** for research organisations to adopt narrative CVs that reflect Open Science values, build transparency, and enable fairer, more holistic researcher assessment.

A **narrative CV** is a structured format that allows researchers to present their achievements and contributions in a qualitative, evidence-based way. Unlike traditional lists of publications or grants, narrative CVs describe the researcher's wider impact on knowledge, people, communities, and society.

Evidence means showing the **reach, use, and relevance** of research contributions.

- *Examples:* citations, altmetrics, downloads, reviews, translations, dataset reuse, FAIR compliance (preferably with persistent identifiers like DOIs, ORCID).

Open Science (OS) (UNESCO, 2021) is about making research inclusive, equitable, and accessible across four pillars:

1. Open scientific knowledge
2. Open science infrastructures
3. Open engagement of societal actors
4. Open dialogue with other knowledge systems

Relevant SCOPE stages

This guide is most relevant for:

- O – Options for evaluating: Identifying diverse contributions beyond publications.
- P – Probe deeply: Gathering robust, evidence-based examples of Open Science practices.

When and how to use

- When:
 - In recruitment, promotion, and funding decisions where a broader view of contributions is needed.
 - When aligning with CoARA, DORA, or other RRA reform initiatives.
- How:
 - Give guidance to researchers on how to use narrative CV templates (e.g., Royal Society's [Résumé for Researchers](#) or UKRI's [R4RI](#)).
 - Train evaluators to recognize OS contributions and assess them with equal weight.
 - Use Figure (below) to map activities across modules.

Guidance

Figure 3 Potential OS activities across narrative CV modules

Module 1 – Knowledge

Prompt: How have you contributed to generating knowledge?

- Tips: Demonstrate transparency in data, methods, and results. Explain responsible limits (e.g., only sharing metadata for sensitive data).
- UNESCO pillar link: *Open scientific knowledge*.
- Examples: Open access papers, preprints, datasets (FAIR), shared code/software, multilingual outputs.

Module 2 – People

Prompt: How have you contributed to the development of individuals?

- Tips: Show how you mentor, train, or support others in adopting OS practices. Highlight inclusivity in supervision and teamwork.
- UNESCO pillar link: *Open scientific knowledge, open engagement of societal actors, open dialogue*.
- Examples: Open educational resources, OS training, mentoring early-career researchers, publishing co-author statements.

Module 3 – Community

Prompt: How have you contributed to the research community?

- Tips: Highlight service roles and community leadership in OS.
- UNESCO pillar link: *Open science infrastructures*.
- Examples: Open peer review, editing for OA journals, OS networks, multilingual scholarly communication, developing OS policies/guidelines.

Module 4 – Society

Prompt: How have you contributed to broader society?

- Tips: Document non-academic dissemination, citizen engagement, and partnerships beyond academia.
- UNESCO pillar link: *Open engagement of societal actors, open dialogue with knowledge systems*.
- Examples: Public engagement, participatory science, multilingual communication, open innovation, recognition of citizen contributions.

Further reading

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resources

- Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>
- Indicators guide 2: Frameworks and Toolboxes for Open Research
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17181862>
- Open science assessment guide <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525630>
- Guide on diversity of OS contributions, roles and activities
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526089>

Other

- The Royal Society. Résumé for Researchers.
<https://royalsociety.org/news-resources/projects/research-culture/tools-for-support/resume-for-researchers/>
- UKRI (2022). Résumé for Research and Innovation (R4RI) template.
<https://www.ukri.org/publications/resume-for-research-and-innovation-r4ri-template/>
- DORA Resource Library: Narrative CV guidance
<https://sfdora.org/resource-library/?keyword=narrative>

- University of Oxford: Guidance on developing narrative CVs
<https://researchsupport.admin.ox.ac.uk/learn-more-about-developing-a-narrative-cv>
- Maastricht University Library: Evidence-based narrative CV guide
<https://library.maastrichtuniversity.nl/research/evaluating-research/research-intelligence/narrative-cv/>
- RoRI (2025): Implementing Narrative CVs: Five Recommendations for Funders
<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.28524755.v1>
- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

4.1.11 Guide on Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) in Research Assessment

Definition

This guide discusses equity, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) as an ethical foundation of research and research assessment (RA). EDI is about ensuring that research environments are safe, fair, and inclusive for individuals across gender, race, ability, career stage, geography, and culture. Embedding EDI in organizational RA policies reduces bias, strengthens integrity, and fosters innovation by embracing diverse perspectives and career paths.

Relevant SCOPE stages

This resource is most relevant for SCOPE stages:

- Options for evaluating: Expanding assessment criteria to recognise diverse outputs, roles, and career paths.
- Probe deeply: Critically examining processes to identify and mitigate biases in recruitment, promotion, and evaluation.

When and how to use

Use this guide when:

- Designing or updating assessment frameworks to include EDI principles.
- Recruiting and promoting staff, ensuring open, transparent, and inclusive processes.

- Evaluating researchers' contributions, especially those with non-linear or interdisciplinary careers.
- Developing institutional policies to align with e.g. ARRA (Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment) and international guidelines.

How to use:

- Broaden recognition → Value a range of outputs (e.g., data, software, mentoring, engagement, multilingual publications).
- Apply fair criteria → Ensure criteria respect disciplinary, career stage, and sectoral differences.
- Ensure accessibility → Address language and disability-related barriers; promote multilingual and accessible outputs.
- Promote inclusivity → Ensure diverse representation in panels, committees, and leadership roles.
- Review regularly → Monitor progress on EDI and update assessment frameworks accordingly.

Guidance

- Principles to embed: Transparency, fairness, inclusivity, accountability.
- Mitigate bias: Train evaluators, use diverse panels, adopt narrative CVs, and recognise non-linear career paths.
- Recognise diverse activities: Reward collaboration, societal engagement, peer review, mentoring, and team science.
- Support accessibility: Adopt Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) and promote multilingual publishing.
- Recruit inclusively: Advertise openly, ensure selection committees are diverse, and align processes with EDI values.
- Everyday practices: Appoint EDI officers, integrate EDI into job descriptions, maintain institutional action plans, and monitor outcomes.

Further reading

- ARRA Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (2022): <https://coara.eu>
- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021): <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMMH8546>
- NWO (2019) Room for everyone's talent: <https://www.nwo.nl/en/position-paper-room-for-everyones-talent>
- Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.7887059>

- Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI): <https://www.w3.org/WAI/>

4.1.12 Checklist for Responsible Assessment

Definition

The Responsible Assessment Checklist is a self-evaluation tool designed to help universities and research organisations ensure their assessment practices align with principles of fairness, transparency, diversity, and accountability. It covers the full cycle of academic and research career assessment: from planning and conducting evaluations to reflecting and improving future processes.

Relevant SCOPE Stages

The checklist supports all five SCOPE stages:

- S – Start with what you value: Ground assessments in institutional mission, strategy, and shared values.
- C – Context considerations: Why are you evaluating and who you are evaluating (e.g., entity size and discipline).
- O – Options for evaluating: Choose diverse methods and indicators, balancing qualitative judgement with responsible use of metrics.
- P – Probe deeply: Consider potential discrimination, gaming of the approach, unintended consequences, and weigh the cost-benefit.
- E – Evaluate your evaluation: Reflect on lessons learned, document decisions, and improve future assessments.

When and How to Use

- When: At all stages of designing, running, and reviewing academic career or research assessment exercises.
- How:
 - Use as a planning tool when setting up evaluation criteria, methods, and teams.
 - Apply as a checklist during implementation to ensure fairness and compliance.
 - Deploy as a reflection framework after completion for learning and improvement.

- Who should use it: HR professionals, evaluators, institutional leaders, and researchers involved in assessment.

Guidance

1. Building the assessment process
 - a. Define values, purposes, objectives, and criteria openly and ensure aligning with relevant RRA reform initiatives (e.g., CoARA).
 - b. Ensure that evaluators are competent, diverse, trained, and free of conflicts of interest.
 - c. Provide clear instructions, transparent guidelines, and fair data practices (including consent and GDPR compliance).
2. Assessing contributions to knowledge
 - a. Prioritise qualitative judgement; use metrics responsibly and only with relevant expertise.
 - b. Avoid reliance on Journal Impact Factor, h-index, or university rankings.
 - c. Enable assessed individuals to review and verify data used.
3. Recognising diverse outputs and activities
 - a. Value a broad range of contributions: publications, datasets, methods, teaching, supervision, leadership, societal interaction, and open science practices.
 - b. Consider career stage, discipline-specific contexts, and different types of opportunities available.
4. After the assessment
 - a. Communicate progress and outcomes clearly to all parties.
 - b. Provide constructive feedback and channels for raising concerns.
 - c. Safeguard sensitive documents and ensure GDPR compliance.
5. Evaluating the assessment process
 - a. Document decisions and reasoning throughout.
 - b. Actively gather feedback from all parties.
 - c. Share lessons learned for continuous improvement across institutions.

Further Reading

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- Open Science Coordination in Finland, Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (2022): Self-Evaluation Tool For Culture Of Open Scholarship Services. [DOI:10.23847/tsv.447](https://doi.org/10.23847/tsv.447)

4.1.13 Guide for evaluating the assessment process

Definition

Evaluating the evaluation is the final stage of the SCOPE Framework, where the effectiveness, fairness, and impact of an assessment are critically reviewed. It ensures that the assessment process itself aligns with principles of responsibility, transparency, inclusivity, and continual improvement.

It involves asking:

- Did the assessment meet its aims?
- Were the processes proportionate, transparent, and fair?
- Were there any unintended consequences?
- How can the next round be improved?

Relevant SCOPE Stages

- E – Evaluate your evaluation: the central stage for this resource.
 - Supported by other stages:
 - S: Clarify values to check alignment.
 - C: Consider context (institutional, disciplinary, cultural).
 - O: Review evaluation methods used.
 - P: Probe deeply for unintended effects.

When and How to Use

When:

- After each assessment cycle (e.g., hiring, promotion, grant selection).
- During reform or transition to Responsible Research Assessment (RRA).
- At fixed intervals, or when problems or unintended effects are identified.

How:

1. Define criteria (relevance, effectiveness, efficiency, transparency, fairness, alignment with RRA principles).
2. Engage stakeholders (e.g., evaluands, evaluators, HR, managers, funders, librarians, research support staff).
3. Collect evidence (surveys, feedback sessions, data on outcomes, unintended effects).

4. Reflect and analyse: Was the process fit for purpose? Did it create trust? Did it achieve institutional goals?
5. Implement improvements: adjust criteria, processes, communication, or training.
6. Share lessons learned internally and, where possible, with other organisations.

Guidance

Principles to apply:

- Relevance: Align with institutional goals.
- Effectiveness: Did intended outcomes occur?
- Efficiency: Were resources proportional?
- Transparency: Was documentation open and accessible?
- Fairness & inclusivity: Were diverse voices considered?
- Alignment: With DORA, CoARA, and other RRA frameworks.

Practical tips:

- Use the GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Checklist for responsible research assessment (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524455>) to structure reflection.
- Apply GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: Stakeholder mapping template (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525686>) to avoid overlooking important groups (technicians, librarians, HR staff, data stewards).
- Ensure feedback loops are built in and visibly acted upon.
- Monitor for unintended consequences (bias, burden, perverse incentives).
- Treat evaluation as ongoing learning, not a one-off compliance exercise.

Further Reading

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- Science Europe (2020): Position Statement and Recommendations on Research Assessment Processes. <https://zenodo.org/records/4916156>
- CoARA (2022): Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. <https://coara.org/agreement/the-agreement-full-text/>

4.1.14 Guide on principles for responsible research assessment for evaluators and evaluands

Definition

Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) is the practice of evaluating researchers and their work in a fair, transparent, and context-sensitive way. It goes beyond narrow metrics (e.g., journal impact factors, h-index) to recognise the diverse contributions researchers make to science and society. RRA encourages:

- Qualitative expert judgement balanced with responsible use of metrics.
- Recognition of diverse outputs (data, software, teaching, community engagement, peer review).
- Attention to open science practices, interdisciplinarity, collaboration, and societal impact.
- Equity and inclusivity by counteracting systemic biases and valuing varied career paths.

This guide is meant both for funders and employers as well as researchers (as reviewers and as subjects of evaluation). It defines the motivation and principles for RRA by introducing a relevant set of regulations and recommendations.

Relevant SCOPE Stages

This guide supports the SCOPE Framework for responsible evaluation (INORMS, 2023). It is most relevant to:

- O – OPTIONS for evaluating: exploring responsible indicators and methods.
- P – PROBE deeply: ensuring criteria, processes, and decision-making reflect RRA principles.

When and How to Use

Use this guide when:

- Designing or revising assessment protocols (e.g., hiring, promotion, tenure, funding).
- Serving on committees making evaluation decisions.

- Preparing for evaluation as an applicant or research leader.

How to apply:

- Employers and funders should define transparent protocols, specify indicators, manage conflicts of interest, and ensure clear communication with evaluators and applicants.
- Researchers as evaluators should have a common understanding of criteria, disclose conflicts, respect confidentiality, and uphold fairness.
- Researchers as evaluands should seek clarification when needed, and report potential conflicts of interest.

Guidance

1. Principles to follow
 - a. Move beyond metrics: Quantitative indicators can be useful but should never substitute expert judgement
 - b. Value diverse contributions: Include outputs like datasets, software, policy engagement, public communication, mentoring, and peer review
 - c. Reward responsible practices: Consider openness, transparency, reproducibility, and ethical conduct as central to evaluation
 - d. Support diversity and equity: Recognise career breaks, non-linear paths, and diverse research cultures
 - e. Foster openness and multilingualism: Recognise contributions in local languages and ensure open research information systems
2. Practical Steps for Organisations
 - a. Assessment design
 - i. Define values and clear criteria right at the beginning
 - ii. Use narrative CVs or structured self-assessments to capture a broad range of contributions
 - iii. Ensure definitions of “quality,” “impact,” and “excellence” are unambiguous and context-specific
 - b. Assessment processes
 - i. Train evaluators to apply RRA principles consistently and to recognise unconscious bias
 - ii. Create diverse and inclusive committees (gender, geography, sector, discipline) to balance perspectives

- iii. Allow for right-to-reply mechanisms so applicants can clarify misunderstandings
 - iv. Monitor and report outcomes, including by gender, discipline, and career stage, to identify systemic inequities
 - c. Recognition and incentives
 - i. Acknowledge a wider set of contributions beyond journal articles, such as
 - 1. merits in teaching and interdisciplinary collaboration
 - 2. reviewing, mentoring, and community service
 - 3. open science practices like sharing data, preprints, or code
3. For Evaluators
- i. Ask for structured review forms that emphasise content, transparency, and responsible indicators
 - ii. Actively resist reliance on journal-based metrics
 - iii. Ask whether outputs show evidence of rigour, reproducibility, openness, and relevance
 - iv. Seek clarification when criteria are unclear or appear inconsistent with RRA commitments
4. For Evaluands
- a. Prepare narrative CVs highlighting the how and why of contributions, not only where they were published.
 - b. Demonstrate broader impacts: show teaching, mentoring, interdisciplinary collaborations, societal engagement, and open science practices.
 - c. Contextualise achievements: explain career breaks, shifts across disciplines, or contributions in local contexts
 - d. Be proactive: request clarification, report conflicts of interest, and flag when criteria are not transparently applied.

Table 2 A visual summary table of the key points of the most relevant RRA principles and guidelines (DORA, The Leiden Manifesto, The Metric tide, The Hong Kong principles, Helsinki initiative, ARRA, Barcelona Declaration). Modified from Pölönen & Mustajoki (2022)

Recommendations		DORA (2012)	LEIDEN (2015)	METRIC TIDE (2015)	HONG KONG (2020)	HELSIN- KI (2019)	ARRA (2022)	BARCE- LONA (2025)
Method	Abandon journal metrics as surrogate measure of quality	✓					✓	
	Quantitative evaluation support qualitative assessment		✓	✓			✓	
	Qualitative judgment based on portfolios		✓					
	Misplaced concreteness and false precision		✓					
	Avoid using university rankings in researcher assessment						✓	
	Commit resources to reforming research assessment						✓	✓
	Raise awareness of research assessment reform						✓	
	Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning						✓	
Support the sustainability of infrastructures for open research information							✓	
Criteria	Explicit criteria used in evaluation	✓						
	Systemic effects of assessment and indicators		✓	✓				
	Scrutiny and regular updating of indicators		✓	✓			✓	
Data	Open and transparent data and methods	✓		✓			✓	✓
	License allowing unrestricted reuse	✓						
	Allowing those evaluated to verify data and analysis		✓	✓				
	Best possible data in terms of accuracy and scope			✓				
Value diversity	All research outputs and broad range of impacts	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
	Missions of the institution, group researcher		✓					
	Excellence in locally relevant research		✓			✓		
	Variation by field in publication and citation practices		✓	✓				
	Plurality of research and career paths			✓			✓	
	Responsible practices, complete reporting, open science				✓		✓	
	Research activities and contributions				✓		✓	
	Multilingualism and outputs in all languages					✓		

Further Reading

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA 2012): <https://sfdora.org/read>
- Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment CoARA (2022): <https://coara.org/agreement/the-agreement-full-text/>
- European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA 2023): <https://allea.org/code-of-conduct>
- Position Statement and Recommendations on Research Assessment Processes Science Europe (2020): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4916156>

4.1.15 Assessment Readiness Template

Definition

The Assessment Readiness Template helps organisations reflect on their maturity in implementing responsible research assessment (RRA). It supports internal discussions, planning, and monitoring by asking structured questions about commitments, policies, expertise, data, and methods. The aim is to ensure that institutions are prepared to conduct evaluations that are transparent, fair, open, and aligned with e.g. CoARA, ARRA, DORA, the Leiden Manifesto, and the Barcelona Declaration.

Relevant SCOPE stages

This resource is most relevant to:

- Start with what you value: Reflecting on commitments, policies, and organisational readiness.
- Context considerations: Understanding the organisational, disciplinary, and cultural context of the assessment process.

When and how to use

Use this template when:

- Beginning the process of RRA reform within your organisation.
- Assessing preparedness before implementing or revising RA frameworks.
- Aligning local policies with international commitments (e.g., CoARA, DORA).
- Engaging multiple departments (HR, administration, library, research offices) in RA planning.

How to use:

- Document commitments → Record existing policies, signatories, and alignment with e.g. CoARA, ARRA, DORA, Leiden Manifesto and Barcelona Declaration.
- Define goals → Clarify whether the assessment is for monitoring, learning, improvement, or resource allocation.
- Describe context → Specify disciplinary traditions, institutional structures, and national/regional conditions.
- Identify resources & expertise → Map which staff and departments are involved, and their experience with RRA and open science.

- List data sources → Review the quality, openness, and verification of data used (e.g., OpenAlex, OpenAIRE, OpenCitations).
- Assess methods → Check how metrics, indicators, and qualitative evaluations are applied.
- Ensure documentation → Record each step of the RA process and set up mechanisms for evaluating the evaluation.

Guidance

- Collaborative process: Complete the template jointly with HR, administrators, librarians, and research managers.
- Check alignment: Ensure policies reflect ARRA principles, DORA guidelines, Leiden principles, and the Barcelona Declaration.
- Balance metrics and judgment: Combine quantitative indicators with qualitative peer review and narrative CVs.
- Use open infrastructures: Prefer non-commercial data sources for transparency and accessibility.
- Address gaps: Identify where expertise, policies, or resources are missing, and plan improvements.
- Integrate EDI: Embed equity, diversity, and inclusion considerations into readiness checks.
- Monitor progress: Use the template periodically to track institutional development.

Further reading

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resources

- Checklist for Responsible Assessment <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524455>
- Institutional assessment process checklist <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526008>

Other

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- ARRA Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment: <https://coara.eu>
- DORA Declaration: <https://sfdora.org/read/>
- Leiden Manifesto: <https://www.leidenmanifesto.org/>
- Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information: <https://barcelona-declaration.org/>

- UKRN Toolkit for Recognising & Rewarding Open Research (2024):
<https://recognition.ukrn-openresearch.ac.uk/>

4.1.16 Guide for Overcoming common obstacles in implementing RRA

Definition

Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) seeks to evaluate research, researchers, and institutions in ways that recognise diverse outputs, practices, and impacts. Instead of relying narrowly on journal metrics or prestige, RRA emphasises qualitative judgment, fairness, openness, and alignment with institutional missions.

This guide summarises common barriers faced by universities and research organisations and outlines practical steps to overcome them.

Relevant SCOPE Stages

This resource links to the SCOPE Framework in the following ways:

- O – OPTIONS for evaluating: choosing how to assess responsibly and inclusively.
- P – PROBE deeply: testing and refining approaches to ensure fairness, feasibility, and alignment with goals.

When and How to Use

Use this resource when:

- Designing or revising career assessment processes (e.g. hiring, promotion, tenure).
- Implementing CoARA or DORA commitments at institutional or departmental level.
- Addressing resistance or confusion about changing assessment practices.

Approach:

1. Map your current practices against SCOPE stages.
2. Identify which obstacles apply (policy, practical, cultural).
3. Select targeted actions (see Guidance) and adapt them to your local context.
4. Engage stakeholders early, especially researchers and leadership.
5. Pilot and iterate, combining qualitative and quantitative evaluation.

Guidance

Common obstacles:

- *Policy*: misaligned national/international rules, lack of incentives, limited institutional autonomy.
- *Practical*: cost concerns, limited staff and data, poor coordination.
- *Cultural*: resistance from researchers or leaders, limited awareness, preference for status quo.

Actions to overcome them:

- Policy collaboration
 - Join international initiatives (CoARA, DORA, Barcelona Declaration).
 - Align institutional policies with broader reform efforts, while allowing flexibility.
 - Advocate nationally for supportive guidelines.
- Investment in infrastructure
 - Develop reliable, open data sources for assessment.
 - Support open infrastructures.
 - Allow the use of structured narrative CVs and qualitative input.
- Culture change strategies
 - Communicate a shared vision.
 - Recognise teamwork, teaching, mentoring, and openness in assessments.
 - Reward peer review and community contributions.
 - Lead by example at senior levels.
- Practical measures
 - Provide staff training on RRA and open science.
 - Engage relevant stakeholders (e.g., researchers) in the process.
 - Simplify new practices (make them easy to use).
 - Pilot innovative schemes (e.g., Recognition & Rewards programmes).

Further Reading

- CoARA (2022). Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. coara.eu/agreement
- DORA (2012). San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment. sf-dora.org
- Hyrkkänen, A.-K. et al. (2023). GraspOS Deliverable D2.1 "OS-aware RRA approaches landscape report". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11098095>
- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

- Stroobants, K. (2024). Can global reform efforts be diverse and aligned? [LSE Impact Blog](#)

4.1.17 Institutional Assessment Process Checklist

Definition

This checklist is a structured tool to support research assessment processes at institutional level. The template is based on the Dutch Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP) 2021–2027, as this approach may be useful beyond the Netherlands in helping research units, executive boards, and assessment committees document, coordinate, and follow up on key stages of an assessment. The focus is on evaluating a research unit against its own aims and strategy, while considering broader aspects such as research quality, societal relevance, viability, open science, academic culture, human resources policy, and PhD training.

Relevant SCOPE Stages

The template is particularly useful in:

- Options: structuring and clarifying how assessment will be organized.
- Probe deeply: ensuring thorough, transparent evaluation and reflection.

When and How to Use

When:

- During planned research assessments
- When developing or reviewing a unit's research strategy.
- To ensure alignment between organizational leadership, research units, and external assessment committees.

How:

- Familiarise yourself with the SEP protocol or your national equivalent.
- Convene all relevant actors (executive board, research unit leaders, impartial expert committee, secretary).
- Complete the template collaboratively, documenting: the unit's aims and strategy, strategic planning discussions, terms of reference and chosen indicators, duties and deliverables for each actor.

- Use the completed template to guide self-evaluation reports, site visits, committee reports, and board responses.
- Ensure outputs (self-evaluation, assessment reports, board responses) feed into the organisation's quality assurance cycle and are made public the agreed time guidance
- For HR and research managers: Use the template to monitor whether diversity, open science, and career development aspects are fully embedded in assessment processes.
- For researchers and unit leaders: Provide evidence of achievements, a SWOT analysis, and forward-looking strategy, emphasising quality, societal impact, and viability.
- For executive boards: Ensure impartial committees are appointed, discussions are documented, and outcomes feed into institutional planning.
- For assessment committees: Reflect objectively on the unit's performance, covering both strategic aims and broader academic culture.

Practical tip:

- Treat the process as iterative and consultative, not purely administrative.

Further Reading

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS, 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP) 2021–2027 (VSNU, KNAW, NWO, 2020): https://www.nwo.nl/sites/nwo/files/documents/SEP_2021-2027.pdf

4.1.18 SCOPE+i Framework training course in OpenPlato

A training course for GraspOS SCOPE+i Framework is available in the OpenPlato learning environment which is a collaborative, e-learning platform developed by OpenAIRE: OpenPlato course GraspOS Opening Research Assessment Training Catalogue [Course: Opening Research Assessment Training Catalogue | OpenPlato](#).

SCOPE+i Framework as key result of GraspOS is available in [Section: SCOPE+i Framework | Opening Research Assessment Training Catalogue | OpenPlato](#).

About course material "SCOPE+i Resources":

Get to know

- Why familiarize yourself with SCOPE+i Resources

- What are SCOPE+i Resources
- What is the contents of SCOPE+i Resources
- Basic idea of the SCOPE Framework
- How SCOPE+i Resources are aligned with SCOPE phases
- Where can you find SCOPE+i Resources
- Re-use permissions of SCOPE+i Resources

Learning objectives

After completing the course section the learner

- utilizes SCOPE+i Resources e.g. templates to fit their organization's needs
- utilizes, applies and adapts SCOPE+i Resources in RRA processes and in training and/or orientation sessions they are involved in
- is aware of the variety of OS contributions and activities
- understands the practical purpose of the five phases of SCOPE Framework

4.2 SCOPE+i Services

The two services are an **Assessment Protocol Portfolio** for use during the full assessment event and an **Openness Profile** – a portfolio for making visible contributions to OS. These services are part of the GraspOS Open [Infrastructure](#) (D4.5) and are technologically underpinned by the Research Activity Identifier, also known as RAiD. Adaptation of the RAiD for use in research assessment was developed in collaboration with the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.

Figure 4 SCOPE+i services in the GraspOS infrastructure

As part of the broader GraspOS infrastructure, the SCOPE+i services offer three key advantages:

- **Collaborative and Inclusive** – Open to all assessment participants.
- **Comprehensive Support** – Accommodates all aspects of assessment planning, documentation, and final protocol development.
- **Interoperable and Extensible** – Built on a robust metadata schema and API, enabling direct data transfer to downstream analytic services.

Additionally, individual instances of these Assessment Protocol Portfolios and Openness Profiles can be hierarchically linked. Figure 5 illustrates this in the context of a hiring committee. Moreover, the Openness Profile can link contributions for assessment at broader levels of aggregation—such as institutes, departments, and universities. Such linking creates a unified record for the hiring committee (keeping all information in one place) while maintaining a clear separation between the published assessment protocol and the evaluands' personal data, thereby enabling individual

Figure 5 illustration of linked entities

Moreover, the Openness Profile can link contributions for assessment at broader levels of aggregation—such as institutes, departments, and universities. Such linking creates a unified record for the hiring committee (keeping all information in one place) while maintaining a clear separation between the published assessment protocol and the evaluands' personal data, thereby enabling individual

consent on privacy. This scalable and access-controlled capacity is enabled by the Research Activity Identifier (RAiD), which is described below.

The role of the SCOPE+i Services is to technologically augment the assessment processes. This weaving of process and digital infrastructure aims to encourage the development of new research assessment practices that allow for contextualization and experimentation. The SCOPE+i Services also facilitate the ingesting of both process and assessment outcomes into existing current research information systems (CRIS) and related services. Each instance of the two services is assigned a Persistent Identifier (PID), which is linked to an editable metadata record.

4.2.1 SCOPE+i Services underpinned by Research Activity Identifier (RAiD)

The SCOPE+i services use the RAiD (Research Activity Identifier), a new persistent identifier (PID) developed by the Australian Research Data Commons⁶ (ARDC). RAiD is designed specifically for research projects and activities and at its core, RAiD consists of two key elements:

- a unique, resolvable DOI, and
- an associated metadata record.

Together, these elements connect organisations, people, inputs, and outputs to specific research projects. RAiD functions as a container for other PIDs (e.g., ORCIDs, RORs, DOIs), linking the different research objects and activities, and tracks their development over time. Each RAiD record includes persistent identification alongside an editable metadata record, allowing updates as the project evolves. Figure 6 illustrates how RAiD can be adapted for an assessment project, with basic assessment information shown on the left side of the diagram and assessment-related content on the right.

⁶ Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) <https://ardc.edu.au/>

SCOPE+i
Protocol Portfolio

(illustration of metadata record)

Title (primary): Assessment, Lorem Ipsum
Title (acronym): ALP
Description: Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Sed non risus. Suspendisse lectus tortor, dignissim sit amet.

Principle investigator: orcid.org/0000-0003-1122-3344
Role: https://credit.niso.org/contributor-roles/conceptualization/
Lead organisation: ror.org/00rqy9422
Partner organisation: ror.org/03b94tp07

Contributor (evaluator): orcid.org/0000-0002-5566-7788
Contributor (evaluator): orcid.org/0000-0001-9900-1234
Contributor (evaluator): orcid.org/0000-0004-2233-4455

Grant: doi.org/10.8948/908234D93EAF
Description (acknowledgement): Pellentesque congue. Ut in risus volutpat libero pharetra tempor. Cras vestibulum bibendum augue. Praesent egestas leo in pede.

 <https://raid.org/10.12345/j6k28>

Related Object # 1: doi.org/10.1000/fakerep0001
Assessment value statement
 Related Object # 2: doi.org/10.5555/testdoi2024-01
Assessment purpose and context statement
 Related Object # 3: doi.org/10.2147/imaginary.202
Narrative CV(s)

Related Object # 4: doi.org/10.3000/mockdata.abc
Assessment dataset(s)
 Related Object # 5: doi.org/10.7777/sample.2024
Assessment service(s)
 Related Object # 6:
Indicators framework
 Related Object # 7:
Indicators toolbox

Related Object # 8:
Assessment Protocol
 Related Object # 9:
Evaluation of the evaluation report

Figure 6 Illustration of Assessment Protocol Portfolio

System architecture and operation

The SCOPE+i services make use of RAiD's system's distributed architecture enabling global adoption while ensuring centralised resolution via raid.org. Functionality relevant for research assessment workflows includes:

- Providing a single, authoritative source of truth for an assessment protocol
- Enabling collaborative, multi-party project administration across institutions
- Generating standardised landing pages for for transparency and inclusivity
- Supporting hierarchical relationships between assessment ...
- Tracking project changes and evolution with versioned metadata

RAiDs are ingested in the Datacite PID Graph⁷ and the EOSC RDGraph⁸, which supplies structured metadata to Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs).

The adaptation of RAiD for use in research assessment was undertaken in collaboration with the FAIRCORE4EOSC⁹ project. Through this collaboration, a RAiD Registration Agency was technically implemented at SURF¹⁰ in the Netherlands to serve the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the wider European region. While the RAiD

⁷ EOSC PID Graph <https://support.datacite.org/docs/raids>

⁸ EOSC RDGraph

<https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/eosc-research-discovery-graph-service-rdgraph>

⁹ FAIRCORE4EOSC website <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>

¹⁰ SURF, the IT cooperative of education and research in the Netherlands

<https://www.surf.nl/en/themes/open-science/open-research-information/research-activity-identifier-raid>

system is now operational at SURF, it has not yet been authorised for full production service. Final approval to launch the RAiD production service at SURF is anticipated by year-end. As a consequence of the RAiD timeline, the GraspOS pilots were not able to test the assessment protocol portfolio or openness profile in a production setting¹¹. However, it was tested by creating a demo version.

4.2.2 Openness Profile

The primary goal of the Openness Profile is to make Open Science (OS) activities visible as a distinct and independent information entity, thereby promoting a more diverse and comprehensive consideration of OS in research and related assessment processes.

The Openness Profile supports the diversity of Open Science contributions by allowing flexible input of various types of content, including both quantitative and qualitative information. Qualitative information is captured through narratives, which enable structured, evidence-based input to support research assessment.

The Openness Profile provides a dedicated narrative field for users to contextualize their contributions to Open Science. A dedicated narrative CV template is being developed within the GraspOS project. These narratives can be supported by the Openness Profile, where relevant evidence-based input is included. Quantitative information refers to data that can be measured or counted using numerical values.

The Openness Profile can also be used in assessment contexts, either directly or as a general-purpose portfolio. In direct use cases, OS contributions recorded in an Openness Profile can be integrated into local assessment infrastructures. Alternatively, the Openness Profile can function as a portfolio of all relevant contributions—OS-related or otherwise—for a specific assessment event. In both cases, Assessment Protocol Portfolios and Openness Profiles can be hierarchically linked. For instance, linked information may share a common landing page and be accessible through an API.

¹¹ Himanen, L. (2025). Deliverable 5.3: Pilot findings and progress report (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17035609>

4.2.2.1 USE CASES

The Openness Profile serves multiple purposes and can be applied across various stakeholder groups. These use cases informed the development of the Openness Profile's metadata schema in RAiD, which is described in Annex 2. For example, the following scenarios illustrate its applications:

1. Researcher (Early Career)

Description: A PhD student or postdoc conducting original research in a university or research institute. Actively seeks out tools and platforms that support open access, reproducibility, and FAIR data practices.

Use case: Uses preprint servers to share findings early, deposits datasets in open repositories, and documents code in Jupyter Notebooks to facilitate reproducibility.

2. Policy Maker

Description: Works for a national funding agency, research ministry, or intergovernmental organization. Focuses on developing and enforcing policies that promote openness, equity, and transparency in research.

Use case: Designs mandates that require publicly funded research to be openly accessible and promotes investment in national PID infrastructure.

3. Community Organizer / Advocate

Description: Works for a non-profit, grassroots initiative, or regional alliance that advocates for equitable access to scientific knowledge. Often bridges gaps between researchers, institutions, and the public.

Use case: Promotes multilingual repositories and open science training in underrepresented regions to ensure inclusion and diversity in global research efforts.

4. Citizen Scientist

Description: A member of the public who contributes to scientific research, often through data collection or analysis, typically in environmental science, health, or astronomy.

Use case: Engages with platforms that host open datasets and tools, contributing observations that enhance large-scale research projects.

5. Indigenous Knowledge Steward

Description: A community leader, researcher, or activist who works to ensure indigenous knowledge systems are respected and integrated ethically into open science.

Use case: Collaborates with institutions to develop culturally appropriate data governance models that ensure sovereignty over data and research outputs.

6. Research Software Engineer (RSE)

Description: Develops software used in academic research. Often situated between traditional academic research and software development.

Use case: Publishes open-source code, contributes to containerized workflows, and ensures proper metadata and licensing to support reproducibility.

7. Data Steward / Data Manager

Description: Supports researchers in managing, curating, and sharing research data in line with FAIR principles. Often employed in academic libraries or research institutes.

Use case: Provides guidance on data management plans, selects appropriate repositories, and ensures use of persistent identifiers.

8. Open Access Publisher / Editor

Description: Works in publishing, whether for a non-profit, university press, or commercial entity, committed to making research openly available.

Use case: Implements transparent peer review, ensures licensing clarity (e.g., CC BY), and integrates with PID systems and metadata standards.

9. Technologist

Description: Non-academic staff that works for a library, or consortia, or commercial company in the scholarly communication space or start-up.

Use case: May or may not write computer code as part of their role, but would be involved in the creation of technologies that support open research. They may be a project manager, solutions architect, technical manager, or entrepreneur.

4.2.2.2 USER GUIDE: OPENNESS PROFILE

The Openness Profile is flexible: it can serve as a direct input to research assessment processes or as a personal portfolio for showcasing Open Science contributions across a researcher's career. One can record qualitative and quantitative information in the Openness profile record.

- Qualitative information: narratives that describe and explain your Open Science practices (e.g. open data sharing, community engagement). These are structured, evidence-based stories that support assessment. A narrative CV template from the GraspOS project will be available during piloting.

- Quantitative information: Measurable data, such as number of datasets published, open-access articles, or contributions to shared infrastructures.

The use opportunities of the Openness Profile depends on the context and the persona involved:

1. For Researchers (Early Career)

Researchers can document their open practices, from publishing preprints and datasets to sharing reproducible workflows. Narratives allow them to explain why and how they engage in openness, while quantitative entries (e.g., number of open datasets) provide measurable evidence.

Use in assessment: Demonstrates diverse contributions beyond publications (e.g., open code, open peer review) in grant or hiring evaluations.

2. For Policy Makers

Policy makers can use aggregated Openness Profiles to understand how open science policies are being implemented in practice. By linking individual profiles to assessment infrastructures, they gain evidence for shaping mandates and tracking progress toward openness goals.

Use in assessment: Provides accountability and measurable impact of policy interventions.

3. For Community Organizers / Advocates

Community advocates can highlight diverse and inclusive practices (e.g., multilingual repositories, open training initiatives) captured in profiles. These narratives ensure that local and grassroots contributions are visible alongside traditional academic outputs.

Use in assessment: Makes visible activities that promote equity, diversity, and inclusion in research ecosystems.

4. For Citizen Scientists

Citizen scientists can use the profile to record their contributions to open datasets, collaborative projects, or data collection efforts. This creates recognition pathways for non-institutional participants.

Use in assessment: Offers legitimacy and visibility for contributions that strengthen research at scale.

5. For Indigenous Knowledge Stewards

The profile allows stewards to document culturally appropriate openness practices while safeguarding sovereignty and sensitive data. Narratives capture context and values, ensuring ethical integration into open science.

Use in assessment: Ensures indigenous knowledge systems are recognised while respecting rights and governance frameworks.

6. For Research Software Engineers (RSEs)

RSEs can showcase their open-source contributions, containerised workflows, and software metadata practices. These often overlooked outputs become visible, measurable, and valued.

Use in assessment: Provides recognition for technical contributions that underpin reproducible research.

7. For Data Stewards / Data Managers

Data professionals can document data management support, repository selection, and PID integration as evidence of enabling FAIR practices.

Use in assessment: Ensures that stewardship and infrastructure contributions are visible alongside research outputs.

8. For Open Access Publishers / Editors

Publishers can use profiles to show commitments to transparency (e.g., open peer review, licensing clarity) and integration with global PID standards.

Use in assessment: Demonstrates how publishing practices contribute to systemic openness.

9. For Technologists

Technologists in libraries, consortia, or startups can record tools, platforms, or infrastructures developed to support open science. Narratives can describe design choices and user impacts.

Use in assessment: Provides recognition for technical and infrastructural contributions that are otherwise invisible in traditional metrics.

Integration with Assessment Protocol Portfolios (APPs)

In assessment contexts, Openness Profiles can be:

- Directly integrated into local infrastructures, providing structured input into hiring, promotion, or funding evaluations.
- Linked hierarchically with APPs, creating a shared landing page and accessible API, ensuring that openness contributions are considered alongside broader assessment protocols.

In summary: the Openness Profile can be used individually (as a personal record of Open Science practices), institutionally (to support fairer research assessments), or systemically (to track and inspire policy, infrastructure, and community development).

4.2.3 Assessment Protocol Portfolio

The SCOPE+i Assessment Protocol Portfolio (APP) supports the planning and documentation of research assessment by serving two main functions: it records the agreed approach for a specific assessment event, and it provides a way to register the assessment protocol once the event concludes. In this way, it acts both as a shared resource for conducting the assessment and as a record of its outcomes.

An APP is a collaborative, multi-actor digital object that consolidates key information for assessment planning. This includes a readiness self-assessment, values and purpose statements, and the assessment protocol itself, which outlines the agreed assessment approach.

During the assessment, the APP is accessible ("locally open") to all participants involved in the event. Afterward, it can also be made publicly available, balancing transparency with the need for confidentiality during the process. This staged openness ensures clarity and consistency for evaluators and those being assessed, while protecting sensitive information during the event.

When an assessment concludes, the APP can be archived for historical reference. The assessment protocol—separated from any privacy-related content—can also be published in the APP Registry (see figure 4 above). Publishing protocols promotes

transparency, reuse, and mutual learning, turning the registry into a community resource that informs and inspires the design of future assessment events.

In the context of this project, an APP will be implemented via a Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) service point for piloting the service. Each registered protocol can be assigned a persistent identifier and a metadata record, to ensure long-term accessibility and make the information suitable for public use. While a user interface is available for administering access and compiling content (useful for smaller tasks), the service is ideally integrated into local platforms via API.

4.2.3.1 USE CASES

These use cases informed the development of the Assessment event's metadata schema in RAiD, which is described in Annex 3.

1. Research Institution Evaluator

Description: A university research office planning an internal assessment of research units. They need a structured, transparent way to define the criteria, values, and methods of the evaluation.

Use case: The evaluator uses the APP to co-create an agreed protocol with stakeholders, ensuring clarity and fairness, while documenting the process for accountability and future reference.

2. Assessed Research Group

Description: A department or research group undergoing an assessment. They need to understand the scope, purpose, and values guiding the evaluation, and to have confidence that sensitive data is protected.

Use case: The group accesses the APP during the event to follow the agreed approach, provide input where relevant, and later use the archived protocol as evidence of the evaluation's fairness and transparency.

3. External Funder or Policy Maker

Description: A funding body or national research council seeking to improve evaluation practices across institutions. They want access to prior protocols to learn from best practices.

Use case: The funder consults the Assessment Protocols Registry to discover published protocols, compare approaches across contexts, and design future assessment frameworks aligned with shared standards and values.

4. Assessment Facilitator/Coordinator

Description: A person responsible for organizing and mediating the assessment process across multiple actors, ensuring coherence and documentation.

Use case: The facilitator uses the APP as the central resource for gathering readiness assessments, purpose statements, and protocols, making sure all participants have consistent access during the event.

5. Wider Research Community

Description: Researchers and institutions interested in improving their own assessment practices through collective knowledge.

Use case: The community accesses the Assessment Protocols Registry to learn from anonymized or published protocols, drawing inspiration and adapting approaches for local needs.

4.2.3.2 USER GUIDE: ASSESSMENT PROTOCOL PORTFOLIO

An Assessment Protocol Portfolio (APP) is a collaborative, multi-actor digital object that brings together the key information for assessment planning and informs the overall assessment design. When used in combination with the Openness Profile (see Figure 5 above), it also supports the delivery of assessment content to downstream analytics via the API.

In the first stages – Start with what you value (S) and Context considerations (C) – of the assessment, a new APP is minted through the RAiD service point. At this stage, contributors are added, and the assessment mandate is described. Documentation includes the readiness self-assessment outcome, a values statement, stakeholder mapping, and contextual factors. These qualitative inputs are recorded in the APP and made available to all participants during the design phase.

In the Options for Assessment (O) stage, the APP provides access to the documented qualitative inputs for consideration in developing the assessment design. This includes the agreed assessment approach, the material to be assessed (e.g., evaluands' narratives, a diversity of contributions), and the planned qualitative and quantitative methods. The result of this stage is a formal assessment protocol, which is recorded in the APP as preparation for performing the assessment.

In the Probe Deeply (P) stage, the protocol and planning documents are available for relevant stakeholders to review potential adverse effects and make adjustments if

needed. This ensures that all participants have access to the full set of assessment materials.

In the final stage, the outcome of the Evaluate your Evaluation (E) step is added to the APP. At this point, the APP is closed and published by simply entering an end date in the relevant field. Once closed, the content is no longer editable but remains accessible to all contributors.

5. Conclusions

The SCOPE+i Framework represents an advancement toward embedding Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) principles into practice. By integrating the SCOPE process with supporting digital services—the Openness Profile and Assessment Protocol Portfolio (APP)—the framework provides both conceptual guidance and practical infrastructure to enable more transparent, equitable, and context-sensitive assessments.

The SCOPE+i Resources form the practical foundation of the framework, translating Responsible Research Assessment principles into actionable steps. A total of seventeen resources have been developed to support all stages of the SCOPE process—from identifying values and defining context to evaluating the evaluation itself.

Presented as templates, guides, and checklists, these resources offer structured yet adaptable support for institutions and communities engaging in assessment reform. They enable consistent documentation of assessment design choices, stakeholder involvement, and contextual factors, ensuring that qualitative inputs are captured alongside quantitative evidence. By providing a shared vocabulary and clear process pathways, the SCOPE+i Resources facilitate collaboration, transparency, and comparability across diverse assessment settings while leaving ample room for local adaptation and experimentation.

Together with the SCOPE+i digital services, these resources complete the framework's dual structure—combining process guidance with interoperable infrastructure. This integration, underpinned by the Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) and developed in collaboration with FAIRCORE4EOSC, ensures that assessment activities, protocols, and outcomes can be persistently linked, shared, and reused across systems and institutions. In doing so, it supports cumulative learning and compatibility within the EOSC ecosystem.

Evidence from the GraspOS pilots reaffirms that context must remain central to assessment design; the SCOPE+i Framework is intended to facilitate, rather than constrain, local adaptation. The framework demonstrates that collaboration and inclusivity are not only aspirational principles but also integral to its technical and procedural design. By enabling multiple actors—researchers, evaluators, funders, and facilitators—to co-create and document assessment processes, SCOPE+i supports a careful balance between transparency and confidentiality while fostering shared ownership of assessment practices. This collaborative approach reinforces trust, promotes comparability, and builds institutional capacity for responsible and sustainable assessment reform.

In summary, the SCOPE+i Framework bridges policy commitments with actionable infrastructure, with the aim of enabling institutions to move from principles to practice in research assessment. It opens the way for more inclusive, transparent, and context-sensitive evaluations that recognise the diversity of research contributions and foster a culture of responsible assessment across the European Open Science landscape.

This interoperability is not only conceptual but also technical, demonstrated through the integration of the SCOPE+i services with the Research Activity Identifier (RAiD). The adaptation of RAiD for use in research assessment was carried out in collaboration with the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, leading to the technical implementation of a RAiD Registration Agency at SURF in the Netherlands to serve the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the wider European region. Although full production deployment is still pending, the groundwork established through this collaboration provides a strong foundation for future testing and operational use of the Assessment Protocol Portfolio and Openness Profile services.

6. Annexes

Annex 1. Reference list and links to GraspOS SCOPE+i Resources

Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Guide for assembling an assessment team**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525548>

Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Value statement template**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524532>

Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Purpose and context statement template**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525469>

Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Guide on choosing an assessment method**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525721>

Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Stakeholder mapping template**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525686>

Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>

Tatum, Clifford (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Indicators Guide 2: Frameworks and toolboxes for open research**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17181862>

Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Open Science assessment guide**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525630>

Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Guide on the diversity of OS contributions, roles and activities**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526089>

Koivisto, Elina, & Sipola, Tiina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525987>

Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Guide on equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) in research assessment**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526122>

Koivisto, Elina, & Sipola, Tiina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Checklist for responsible research assessment**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524455>

Koivisto, Elina, & Sipola, Tiina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Guide for evaluating the assessment process**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526189>

Koivisto, Elina, & Sipola, Tiina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Guide on principles for responsible research assessment for evaluators and evaluands**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526025>

Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Assessment readiness template**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525577>

Koivisto, Elina, & Sipola, Tiina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Guide for overcoming common obstacles in implementing RRA**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526054>

Sipola, Tiina, & Koivisto, Elina (2025). GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource: **Institutional assessment process checklist**. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526008>

Annex 2. Open Profile Metadata Mapping to RAID schema elements

This section is analyzing usage of existing RAiD metadata schema elements for describing an openness profile. After analyzing existing elements, an extension of RAiD metadata schema is suggested.

- [identifier](#)
 - This should be used for assigning RAiD to an openness profile. This field is mandatory in a RAiD record, but it is not intended to be created by third parties (some platform via API or end user via UI), i.e. this identifier will be automatically created and populated by a RAID service.
- [date](#)
 - An openness profile is linked with a person/researcher for its contribution to open science in a certain period. The beginning of that certain period is preserved in date.startDate while end is date.endDate. It might be for a complete career, meaning in the case of a person startDate is date of birth, or in the case of organization unit it might be foundation date. The end date might be undefined.

- [title](#)
 - Title of the openness profile. For instance, Dragan Ivanovic Openness profile for the period 2020-2025.
- [description](#)
 - Free text composed by the contributor to provide a textured account of their contributions to open scholarship.
- [contributor](#)
 - ORCID number of a person which openness profile is cataloged in the RAID record, or
 - ISNI number of an organization unit which openness profile is cataloged in the RAID record, or
 - set of ORCID numbers of group members which openness profile is cataloged in the RAID record
- [organisation](#)
 - In the context of cataloguing an individual's Openness Profile within a RAiD record, the field for affiliated organisations must be used only to indicate organisational affiliations that contribute to the advancement of Open Science. Therefore, it does not include all institutional affiliations by default (e.g., university, faculty, research center), unless those institutions actively contribute to Open Science infrastructure, policy, or advocacy. Therefore, the linked organisations must have a documented role in promoting Open Access, FAIR data, reproducible research, responsible research assessment, development of open-source research software, etc. For instance, it might be
 - OpenAIRE (<https://ror.org/00cvxb145>) - Open Access infrastructure and policy network
 - CoARA - Reforming research assessment in line with Open Science
 - Research Data Alliance - RDA (<https://ror.org/027mnnb54>) - FAIR data, data sharing standards, community building
 - OpenCitations (<https://ror.org/04aj4c181>) - Open bibliographic metadata and citation transparency
 - Lyrisis(<https://ror.org/03v5cnb98>) - Supports open-source repositories and tools for scholarly communication
 - SPARC Europe (<https://ror.org/03v76x132>) - Advocacy for Open Access, Open Data, and Open Education
 - EOSC Association (<https://ror.org/05jxwwz62>) - European infrastructure for FAIR and Open Science

- [relatedObject](#)
 - These elements link with the specific artefacts, outputs, or contributions related to a person's Open Science activities. [relatedObject.category.id](#) is Output (<https://vocabulary.raid.org/relatedObject.category.id/190>). The examples:
 - A researcher who uses open platforms and tools to make their work FAIR and reproducible (practicing open science):
 - Preprint (<https://metadata.raid.org/en/latest/core/relatedObjects.html#relatedobject-type-id>) – early dissemination of research prior to peer review.
 - Dataset – openly shared data supporting findings or methods.
 - Software – scripts or code used for data analysis or simulation.
 - Workflow – automated processing pipelines (e.g., Snakemake, Nextflow).
 - Computational Notebook - for instance documents code in Jupyter Notebooks to facilitate reproducibility
 - Report - open peer-review
 - A research software engineer or technologist (librarian, developer, etc.) who develops and maintains software for research, contributing to technical reproducibility.
 - Software – open-source software which helps in conducting research, dissemination of research results or finding researchers/experts.
 - Workflow – reusable workflows or pipelines supporting reproducible research.
 - Service – infrastructure components or APIs that enable Open Science.
 - Community organizer or advocate who promotes Open Science through community building, training, or policy engagement.
 - Event – organised trainings, workshops, or advocacy campaigns.
 - Report – outcome documents or white papers from open science working groups or initiatives.

- Report - Open Science strategies or recommendations co-developed with communities.
 - Note: Extension of the types vocabulary (<https://metadata.raid.org/en/latest/core/relatedObjects.html#relatedobject-type-id>) might be useful here, Report is not a perfect choice for the object type in this case.
- Policy maker who shapes research systems to be more transparent and accessible through policy development.
 - Report – public mandates or funding requirements supporting Open Science.
 - Note: Extension of the types vocabulary (<https://metadata.raid.org/en/latest/core/relatedObjects.html#relatedobject-type-id>) might be useful here, Report is not a perfect choice for the object type in this case.
 - Report – strategic documents or implementation roadmaps.
 - Standard – technical or procedural frameworks supporting openness and interoperability.
- Open access publisher or editor who ensures scholarly publishing aligns with Open Access principles.
 - Report – peer review policies, or licensing guidelines.
 - Note: Extension of the types vocabulary might be useful to support Policy
 - Workflow - editorial workflows
- Data Steward or Data Manager who Supports researchers in curating, managing, and sharing data according to FAIR principles. Commonly works in academic libraries or research institutes.
 - Dataset – curated, documented, and openly available research datasets with persistent identifiers and metadata.
 - Output Management Plan– data management plans (DMPs), curation protocols, or documentation that outlines FAIR practices and repository usage.
- Indigenous knowledge steward who ensures indigenous knowledge is represented ethically and with sovereignty in Open Science.
 - Report – culturally grounded data governance frameworks.

- Event – community-led engagements or consultations.
 - Report – documentation of ethical practices and collaboration outcomes.
- [alternateIdentifier](#)
 - Local identifier of the researcher profile in the local CRIS system for instance, or it might be ScopusAuthorID, or ResearcherID (Web of science), OpenAlex identifier, etc.
- [alternateURL](#)
 - The web page where researcher openness profile is visualized (for instance in the [research.fi](#) or [BIP!Scholar](#))
- [relatedRaid](#)
 - This element might be used for establishing connection with a Research activity (project) which is contributing to Open Science. The relatedRaid.type is isPartOf (<https://vocabulary.raid.org/relatedRaid.type.schema/202>).
 - The examples:
 - A researcher or research software engineer (or technologist) who participates in a research/infrastructure/software project which is producing results which contribute to development of Open Science or boosting its adoption.
 - A researcher who is an advisor of a PhD project contributing to Open Science.
 - A citizen who participates in a citizen science project.
 - A research software engineer (or technologist) who participates in a software project which is producing open-source software.
- [access](#)
 - Open (https://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/access_rights/c_abf2/)
- [subject](#)
 - Research field and keywords linked with researcher or organization for whom Openness Profile is being created. The purpose of this is to make it easier to be found.

Potential extensions of the RAiD schema

Besides related objects (<https://metadata.raid.org/en/latest/core/relatedObjects.html>), it would be useful to have structure for related activities. This could also capture activities contributing to Open Science which did not produce output artefact (article, report, etc.). Those activities might be outreach lectures related to Open Science, participation

in a working group related to Open Science (some RDA working group), participation in a journal editorial board, etc.

In the case of using a RAiD record for describing a person profile in relation to the relatedObject ((<https://metadata.raid.org/en/latest/core/relatedObjects.html>) it would be useful that the role of the person can be defined (data-curator, author, etc.).

Vocabulary of related object types

(<https://metadata.raid.org/en/latest/core/relatedObjects.html#relatedobject-type-id>)

might be extended with following types: Policy, Guidelines, Framework, Review, Proposal, Protocol, Research Technique, Methodology, Tool, Artwork, Syllabus.

Annex 3. An Assessment Event Metadata Mapping to RAID schema elements

This section is analyzing usage of existing RAiD metadata schema elements for describing an assessment event. After analyzing existing elements, an extension of RAiD metadata schema is suggested. New fields suggested in this extension should enable complete cataloging of different elements of research assessment projects. It could describe scope of the assessment, as well as data and metrics used in the assessment.

- [identifier](#)
 - This should be used for assigning RAiD to a research assessment project.
- [date](#)
 - This should be used for dates in which assessment exercise was completed. Please make a distinction between this and the time frame of assessed objects. For instance, an assessment was conducted in the period March 1st - April 30th 2023 (date.startDate = 2023-03-01, date.endDate = 2023-04-30), and it assessed all results in the period 1/1/2021-12/31/2022. The last dates will be in assessmentScope.temporalCoverage.startDate and assessmentScope.temporalCoverage.endDate.
- [title](#)
 - Title of the assessment project. For instance, Self-evaluation of scientific production for University of Novi Sad for the two-year period 2021-2022. There has to be at least one title, but might be more (title.type.id = primary, acronym, alternative, or short).

- [description](#)
 - Free text description of the assessment project.
- [contributor](#)
 - List of committee members who are conducting the assessment process. There might also be contributors who voted committee members or approved their final report.
- [organisation](#)
 - Institution which is organizing assessment. For instance, the University of Novi Sad (RPO) or some funding agency (RFO).
- [relatedObject](#)
 - Assessment infrastructure resources (value statement, purpose statement, etc.), submitted CVs of candidates (narrative CV), etc. Please make a distinction between submitted CVs mentioned here and Openness Profiles. Submitted CVs are documents which might be preserved in Zenodo or some other repository, while Openness Profiles are RAiD records, and therefore Openness Profiles are linked by using a relatedRaid field.
- [alternateIdentifier](#)
 - Local identifier of the assessment process, for instance from the institutional CRIS system
- [alternateURL](#)
 - The web page where assessment is announced (for instance call for application for funding).
- [relatedRaid](#)
 - This element might be used for establishing connection with other related assessment tasks. Moreover, this can be used to link funding agency assessment projects with the project awarded for funding. Also, the linked RAID might be the Openness Profiles of applicants who should be evaluated.
- [access](#)
 - Open (https://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/access_rights/c_abf2/)
- [subject](#)
 - Research field and keywords linked with assessment
- [spatialCoverage](#)
 - If assessment level is a country or region this field can be used

Potential extensions of the RAiD schema

The proposed extension of the RAiD schema should enable more structured description of an assessment event, which should make it possible to filter out and search Assessment Protocols Registry in a more powerful way and thus fulfill use case number 5 (wider research community) more effectively. Documented assessment events can be browsed from the Registry e.g. by method and metrics, goal of the assessment, entity, temporal coverage, used data.

- assessmentScope
 - A metadata schema block containing the description of the scope of the research assessment and associated properties. The field includes the following structure:
 - method - represent a vocabulary aligned with common structure of other RAiD vocabularies, meaning there is the id subfield with vocabulary terms, and the scheme field with defined vocabulary schema.
 - id
 - metrics only,
 - expert assessment (peer-review) only,
 - expert assessment supported by metrics
 - schemaUri
 - assessmentMethodSchema
 - goal - this is a vocabulary field
 - id
 - strategic priorities,
 - research evaluation policy,
 - hiring and promotion policies,
 - institutional or unit mission statement,
 - evaluation principles,
 - collective values,
 - application for funding
 - schemaUri
 - assessmentGoalSchema
 - level - this is a vocabulary field
 - id
 - individual,
 - group of researcher,
 - institution,
 - country,
 - research field
 - schemaUri

- assessmentLevelSchema
 - temporalCoverage - this should be used for results dates period. Only results from this period are assessed, for instance the period might be 1/1/2021-12/31/2022.
 - startDate
 - e.g. 2021-01-01
 - endDate
 - e.g. 2022-12-31
- assessmentData
 - A metadata schema block containing the description of the data which are assessed in the project. The field includes the following structure:
 - capturing
 - quantitativeSource - a vocabulary
 - id
 - Data are submitted/uploaded in unstructured formats (templates are provided, structured web formats are specified, detailed instructions are given, etc.)
 - Using altmetrics databases (i.e. PlumX, Altmetric.com, etc.)
 - Data are submitted/uploaded in structured formats (i.e. templates are provided, structured web formats are specified, detailed instructions are given, etc.)
 - Using global academic databases (i.e. Web of Science, Scopus, ORCID, CrossRef, etc)
 - Data are submitted/uploaded using local platforms/data sources
 - schemaUri
 - capturingQuantitativeSourceSchema
 - qualitativeSource - a vocabulary
 - id
 - Surveys
 - Narrative CV
 - Competency-based CV
 - Evidence-based CV
 - Impact stories or case narratives
 - Structured CV
 - schemaUri
 - capturingQualitativeSourceSchema

- type - a vocabulary. Please note the three vocabularies schemas with associated list of terms are suggested to be introduced in the extension (CoARAResearchOutputs, CoARAActivitiesAndRoles, CoARAContributionToOpenScience).
 - id
 - Scientific publications
 - Datasets
 - Software
 - Policy contributions
 - Methods
 - Protocols
 - Exhibitions
 - Theories
 - Strategies
 - Algorithms
 - Data models
 - Workflows
 - schemeld
 - CoARAResearchOutputs
- type
 - id
 - Industry-academia cooperation
 - Training, mentoring and supervision of PhD candidates
 - Teaching
 - Peer review
 - Leadership roles
 - Entrepreneurship
 - Science communication and interaction with society
 - Team science and collaboration
 - Skills, competence and merits
 - Knowledge valorization
 - Roles outside of academia
 - Diverse contributor roles (Data steward, software engineer, and data scientists)
 - Citizens science
 - schemeld
 - CoARAActivitiesAndRoles
- type
 - id

- Open access publishing
 - Data sharing
 - Open peer-review
 - Pre-prints
 - Research plans
 - Software sharing
 - Method sharing
 - schemeld
 - CoARAContributionToOpenScience
- assessmentMetrics
 - A metadata schema block containing the description of the metrics used in the assessment project. The field includes the following structure:
 - name - a free text field
 - e.g. h-index, number of publications, citations, etc.
 - type - a vocabulary field
 - id
 - Research output level metrics (citations, downloads, etc.)
 - Individual researcher level metrics (e.g. counting papers, patents, citations, grants, h-index, etc.)
 - Metrics relating to publication venue (e.g. Journal Impact Factor)
 - schemaUri
 - assessmentMetricsSchema
 - source - a free text field
 - e.g. WoS, Dimensions, BIP! Indicators, etc.
 - url - an URL
 - e.g.
<https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/site/indicators#Popularity-alt>